

**First record of *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830)
(Heteroptera: Reduviidae) in Kalecik District
(Prov.Ankara, Türkiye)**

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ABSTRACT: *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae), a rare species in nature, was recorded in Kalecik District (Ankara, Türkiye). This is the first record of *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830) from Kalecik.

KEYWORDS: *Sphedanolestes pulchellus*, first record, Kalecik district, Ankara, Türkiye

The suborder Heteroptera (Hemiptera) has more than 45,000 species/subspecies worldwide (Henry, 2017). So far, approximately 33,820 species belonging to the class Insecta have been recorded in Türkiye (Tezcan, 2020). Among these, 1668 species/subspecies belong to the suborder Heteroptera (Hemiptera) (Çerçi et al., 2024). In the Palaearctic region, there are 9400 species/subspecies belonging to 1,632 genera (Aukema et al., 2013; Henry, 2017; Fent & Dursun, 2022). Based on these data, it appears that approximately 18% of the Heteroptera species found in the Palaearctic region are distributed in Türkiye.

The Reduviidae family is the second largest family of Heteroptera with 930 genera and 6800 species in 23 subfamilies worldwide (Putshkov & Putshkov, 1996). In the Turkish Reduviidae fauna, 65 species, 19 genera and 6 subfamilies have been recorded so far (Çerçi et al., 2024).

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Members of the Reduviidae are predators on small arthropods. . They lie in wait for prey on the ground, in or under vegetation, and in flowers. Reduvids are usually seen as solitary in nature (Putshkov & Putshkov, 1996).

In this study, *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830), belonging to the Harpactorinae, recorded from Kalecik, is a rare species with low population density.

According to Aukema (2025), the distribution of *S. pulchellus* in the Palaearctic is Europe, North Africa and Asia.

The distribution of this species in Türkiye is limited to a few provinces given below.

Figure 1. Specimen of *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830), Kalecik /Ankara-Türkiye

REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807

HARPACTORINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus: *Sphedanolestes* Stal, 1867

Sphedanolestes pulchellus (Klug, 1830)

Material examined: Ankara Province: Kalecik-Akkuzulu, 24.VI.2025, 1♂ (Leg. and det. Z. Yaman)

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çankırı, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kocaeli, İstanbul, Tekirdağ (Önder, 1980; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Salur, 2013; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak,2015)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Albania Bosnia Hercegovina Bulgaria Greece

Italy (Sardinia) Macedonia. North Africa: Algeria Egypt Morocco. Asia: Turkey Cyprus Israel Lebanon Syria Yemen (Aukema, 2025).

Comments:

Sphedanolestes pulchellus is a rare species with a low population density in nature. This species was previously recorded by Kiyak (1993) from Soğuksu National Park/ Kızılcahamam (Ankara Province). This study provides the second record of *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* from the Ankara fauna and the first from the Kalecik fauna.

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